

TRAIN4EU

Transforming ReseArch & INnovation
agendas and support in 4EU+

H2020-IBA-SwafS-Support-1-2020

Project no.: **101016674**

Start date of project: **1. January 2021**

Duration of project: **36 months**

Deliverable

Reference number and title:

D 3.3 Report on transformative change potential and piloting, research infrastructure

Name of lead beneficiary:

Heidelberg University

Due date:

30 November 2023

This project has received funding from
the European Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation programme
under grant agreement No 101016674.

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Submission schedule:

Deliverable 3.3	Version	Date	Prepared By
D3.3 final report	1	30 November 2023	WP3 lead UHD
D3.3 revised final report	2	6 May 2024	WP3 lead UHD

1. Description of deliverable 3.3

Report on infrastructural cooperation and piloting potential of Sharing Research Infrastructures and developing research support resources (M35)

Background

WP3 addresses research infrastructure (RI) as technical and physical research infrastructure facilities (e.g. core facilities and instruments, databases, digital libraries) as well as research infrastructure technical support staff, and the centralised research support units, including advisory and administrative services in research support at all stages and levels.

As stated in the WP3 Protocol, submitted as Deliverable 3.1, objectives of the WP include developing a strategy towards sharing resources and infrastructures, and searching for promising models for sharing infrastructures across research groups, with business and students. In Task 3.2, a mapping analysis of the partner universities and their research infrastructure (e.g. core facilities and instruments, databases, digital libraries) was performed, to identify best practices for management and potential for sharing and scaling infrastructure investments. The comprehensive and up-to-date mapping of the existing and planned research infrastructures across the alliance provided a basis for comparison of RI. Additional possibilities for international infrastructure collaborations, cross-University coordination of research infrastructure investments, sharing of experts, and expertise on research support and management, as well as shared experience on management of cost and centralised usage of technical infrastructure were identified as further goals.

Potentials for piloting new models for enhancing the value of research infrastructure through collaboration inside, across and outside of universities within the Alliance were analysed. In addition, possibilities for joint utilisation of core facilities and other research infrastructure in order to facilitate and initiate proposals for joint research projects across partner universities were explored, thus setting a future objective for the European Universities Alliances in research cooperation.

Objectives and approaches

The aim of Task 3.3 was to identify cross-over learning innovation and piloting transformative actions building on the results and on positive and negative lessons learned from Task 3.2. A set of online and physical meetings and workshops was implemented to share the analyses and ideas for new innovative approaches to shared technical infrastructure, as well as support services (on-site and in central research support units) e.g. through knowledge transfer and by re-combining ideas and approaches into new variants. Consultations with selected stakeholders across partner countries to gather further inspiration for innovative and transformative actions on how to share research infrastructures were part of Task 3.3.

The examples of potential stakeholder inclusion analysed in this task related to core facility management systems, such as operational software for allocation of equipment, research management solutions (e.g. support by experienced staff), collaboration platforms and

research coordination offices (fundamental service). Based on the assessment of case studies in research infrastructure facilities, best practice benchmarks and a set of innovations and learning-driven transformations suitable for upscaling across the alliance were identified, demonstrating potential for exploitation by other European universities.

2. Task 3.3. Innovation through re-combination and stakeholder inspiration

2.1. Task 3.3 governance

To deliver the potential for collaboration and pilot actions, the participants of WP 3 held several meetings during the period from August 2022 until November 2023.

The work on Task 3.3 started in August 2022, when the participants met to discuss the first steps towards a piloting potential in the WP. In October, the WP leader presented the results from the first EC REA periodic review meeting held 9 September 2022 during which WP3 received a positive review, alongside some recommendations. Specifically, the reviewers asked for a strategy for development of the topics of WP3 as well as enhanced industrial collaboration.

A subsequent physical meeting planned during Task 3.3 was held in Milan 23-24 March 2023, to assess the best practice for management of the UNITECH Core facilities at the University of Milan. The participants received a thorough presentation of the UNITECH Core Facilities. The visit was followed by a WP-meeting at the University of Milan.

Another presentation of local Core Facilities was organised by the University of Warsaw on 18 September 2023. The WP leader as well as the project coordinator from the University of Copenhagen were present at the meeting.

During the period October 2023 to December 2023 the participants continued to meet regularly online, to discuss further collaboration after the TRAIN4EU project.

The WP leader from Heidelberg University further participated in the SwafS Cross-Alliances Forum 2023 in Brussels on 30 November - 1 December 2023. WP3 represented TRAIN4EU at the Forum's poster session, with a poster highlighting the best practice assessment from the UNITECH Core Facilities at the University of Milan.

Continuous discussion evolved around potential pilot actions, such as workshop series for scientific or administrative staff of Core Facilities and potential for a database for RI facilities. Opportunities for enhanced industrial collaboration would also be addressed at such meetings. A workshop was planned for the fall of 2023 but had to be cancelled due to scheduling difficulties. A networking event planned to take place in the fall of 2024 is intended to be the start of a series of networking events for RI staff. Furthermore, a database for research infrastructure will be part of the future collaboration of RI facilities in the strategic network of 4EU+.

During the first implementation phase of Task 3.3, the University of Milan put forward the idea of a working paper, which would highlight the results of the mapping analysis and present to the public the challenges and opportunities of research infrastructure

management at European Universities (and thus build on the work carried out in all WP3 tasks). The suggestion received overall approval by the WP participants and work on the paper was set to start in November 2023. WP leader circulated the idea of a working paper as a pilot action in WP 3 at the Annual Meeting 2022 in Copenhagen, where issues concerning WP3 were discussed and it was positively met by the coordinators at the University of Copenhagen. Three main points were brought out: 1. RI as physical infrastructures 2. Technicians and staff training 3. Finances of RI facilities. In addition, the issue of shared data and shared experiences were raised, as well as control and validation of data. During the physical meeting in Milan the participants agreed to submit the paper to a peer-reviewed journal.

2.2. Building on Task 3.2 mapping

The TRAIN4EU mapping exercise confirmed the anticipated distribution of research infrastructure facilities between scientific domains, Life Sciences being the domain with most registered Core Facilities at most Universities. Differences were identified e.g. centralised vs. decentralised management systems, whereby the University of Milan displayed the best practice with the UNITECH facilities in terms of centralised management of Core Facilities. In the domain of Natural Sciences some Core Facilities could also be mapped, however these tend to be less organised than Core Facilities in Life Sciences. Some cases mixed scientific domain (Life + Natural Sciences), such as the Core facilities from the University of Warsaw.

A positive finding from the mapping was the relatively large number of facilities, classified as Research Facilities (RF) according to TRAIN4EU parameters, in the Social Sciences and Humanities domains, since these domains usually fall short in terms of research infrastructure at European Universities. Especially facilities dealing with digitalisation in different fields of humanities (and to some extent in social sciences), or Digital Humanities could be found in most of the Universities reviewed. Additionally, some interdisciplinary research facilities were mapped, as well as research support offices at two universities, displaying vast similarities in terms of research support activities.

As centralised and decentralised management emerged as the focal point in the administration of research infrastructure, the assessment of best practice at the University of Milan was the next step towards optimising the management of research infrastructure facilities at all Alliance universities. As the mapping showed, only few research infrastructures are administratively hosted at the central level or at faculty level at most universities. The majority are located in a decentralised manner within different departments. One of the main benefits of this model is closeness (physical, organizational and mental) to the relevant scientists and (domain specific) scientific community, who are the actual and potential users of the equipment.

A disadvantage of the decentralised model is potential lack of visibility and lack of focus on cross-cutting issues and on key objectives of European Infrastructures. These include avoidance of duplication and fragmentation of research infrastructure, better coordination of development and usage of RI, as well as often neglected issues such as training and career development of the specialized staff who are running the scientific equipment. However, while the management and encouragement of research is a prime determinant of organisational structures in all six Alliance universities, there is no „single model“. The key

point emerging from all the universities is that ongoing uncertainty associated with unidentified and unresolved managerial issues leads to research inefficiency.

Other challenges emerging from the mapping analysis were linked to topics such as funding, especially issues regarding operational costs, core funding, staff funded by host institutions, national institutions (ministries), external funders and/or user fees and the need the facilities often face to constantly balance economical existence and scientific relevance in the research network of a university. Staff issues were particularly addressed by all facilities and institutions, since the problematic of sustainable employment for “scientific technical experts” – as they were called during the implementation of Task 3.3 – appears to be omnipresent.

2.3. Cooperation and piloting potential

Possible pilot actions in WP3 were aimed at enhancing the cooperation between research infrastructure facilities at the partner universities across the alliance. Through the extensive mapping analysis, many aspects from facilities in all scientific fields were identified as ground for cooperation and exchange of best practice experience. The 4EU+ joint mapping exercise of the six universities provided the first common mapping of research infrastructures and core facilities across the 4EU+ University alliance and highlighted the best practice of Core Facilities management at UNITECH facilities, University of Milan.

Best practice assessment of UNITECH Core Facilities at the University of Milan

A thorough description of all UNITECH facilities was carried out in Task 3.2. and can be found in the respective deliverable 3.2. At the University of Milan, four research infrastructures called UNITECH are classified as Core Facilities (CF) and are located at the campus of the University of Milan in Italy. UNITECH Core facilities in the scientific domain of Life Sciences are COSPECT, NOLIMITS and OMICs, and in Natural Science INDACO. Keywords for identifying the facility in the general search option in COSPECT are mass spectrometry, NMR spectrometry, X-ray Diffractometry. In NOLIMITS the keywords are Microscopy Services, live imaging, in vivo analysis, Transmitted Optical Microscopy, Fluorescence Optical Microscopy, Electron Microscopy, Cryogenic electron microscopy. OMICs can be characterised by keywords such as Metabolomics, Proteomics, Lipidomics, Peptidomics.

During the WP meeting and best practice assessment at the University of Milan on 23-24 March 2023, the UNITECH facilities were presented to the WP participants. The facilities visited included INDACO, COSPECT, NOLIMITS and OMICs. The presentations consisted of on-site visits to the facilities, including assessment of the equipment, exchange with staff, as well as presentations of the features of the facilities in a subsequent meeting with TRAIN4EU WP participants and facility managers. During the meetings, facility managers and scientific technical experts presented the facilities and answered questions. The following features of UNITECH facilities were addressed: Research activities, past and future prospects of the UNITECH Core Facilities, including the new model for UNITECH 2.0 with 11 facilities planned for 2026, staff and equipment of UNITECH facilities, the current Core Facility model and topics linked to Core Facility accounting. The presentations of all the UNITECH facilities provided further insights into their management models, specific equipment, user details, services and

platforms offered, as well as investment possibilities. Additionally, future perspectives and cooperation interests were discussed.

Overall, the presentation of the UNITECH facilities gave the WP participants a comprehensive overview of the features in place at the University of Milan and revealed considerable potential for future cooperation in the Alliance, as well as insights for possible implementation of the UNITECH management model at their respective universities. Joint research and administrative collaboration within the Alliance between UNITECH facilities and research infrastructure facilities at Alliance universities in the future, however, is greatly dependent on further funding.

Core Facilities at University of Warsaw

The WP leader and project manager were offered an insight into the Core Facilities at the University of Warsaw on 18. September 2023. Here, the laboratory accreditation process at the CNBCH was highlighted, and Core Facilities CeNT and CePT alongside business-academia processes were presented. There was an opportunity to visit the facilities and have a dialogue with the scientists and managers in charge. The insights gathered from the facilities at the University of Warsaw further completed the mapping of the research infrastructure at the universities across the Alliance.

Presentation of WP3 Best Practice at the SwafS Cross-Alliances Forum 2023

In December 2023 the WP leader from Heidelberg University participated in the SwafS Cross-Alliances Forum 2023 in Brussels on 30 November - 1 December 2023. At the Interactive poster session on 30 November which featured presentations of the SwafS projects transformation modules, a WP3 poster highlighted the best practice assessment from the UNITECH Core Facilities at the University of Milan, alongside other results from the work done in WP 3.¹ The Forum gave TRAIN4EU participants the chance to meet and exchange with representatives from other alliances, such as FORTHEM, EUGLOHRIA, EUGLOH, CIVICA, EDUC, Transform4Europe and EPICUR, and discuss findings, lessons learned and future perspectives as well as networking for future collaboration.

3. Transformative actions

Discussions in the participating Universities on transformation, particularly concerning the sharing potential of research infrastructure facilities, was carried out at local level. As already stated in D3.1 and D3.2, there is general lack of centralisation and common architecture, especially concerning technical infrastructure. There are great variations in terms of facilities and equipment, depending on the field of science, funding options and traditions, and focus and interest of scientist and senior management across the alliance. These variations give rise to ambiguities with regard to ownership, funding and usage of infrastructure. Through best

¹ <https://www.charm-eu.eu/mapping-alliances-ri-best-practices>

practice assessment during the TRAIN4EU meeting at the University of Milan, a general need for better management models was identified across the Alliance.

However, a new transformation of the entire research infrastructure network at each university is neither feasible during the lifespan of a single project nor is it desirable from the perspective of the partner universities. Transformative pilot actions thus relate to maintenance and further development of existing networks, consideration of best practices in the local infrastructure networks and integration of future transformative actions in the 4EU+ research strategy. As was already clarified in the initial mapping and protocol (D3.1 and D3.2), initial acquisition and the later operational costs of running RI lead to diverging views among alliance partners with regard to both the exploitation of core facilities or equipment, which depends on the policy of the university or department, as well as to the availability to own scientists and external users, which depends on the policy of funding bodies.

It is therefore not within the mandate of an international collaboration project, such as TRAIN4EU, to decide upon internal university or department policy, but rather propose transformative potential with best practice examples, as was done at each University of the Alliance in TRAIN4EU. At the same time, cases of research infrastructure facilities are particularly prone to political, financial and administrative obstacles to internal collaboration within the university, not to mention those affecting external collaboration across borders. In spite of these hurdles, best practice assessment from TRAIN4EU at the UNITECH facilities of University of Milan revealed great potential for transformative pilot actions at local level, as well as for joint research and collaboration, which we intend to pursue in the future.

3.1. Potential Pilot actions

The WP3 team worked on the following potential pilot actions for transformative collaboration in research infrastructure within TRAIN4EU network:

Workshops for scientific and/or administrative staff at RI facilities

Workshop series, on-site or virtual, for scientific and/or administrative staff of Core Facilities (or other RI facilities) to exchange about potential for joint research, to further explore infrastructure facilities at Alliance universities (as was done in Milan), find common ground for research projects and explore opportunities for staff exchange, both administrative and academic. Opportunities for enhanced industrial collaboration could also be addressed at such meetings. A start-up workshop was initially scheduled in the fall of 2023, however it could not take place due to scheduling difficulties.

Database of research infrastructure

Database of research infrastructure facilities across 4EU+. During the lifespan of TRAIN4EU we experienced only parts of the infrastructure networks at our universities. The facilities presented in the mapping analysis (D3.2) showed great variation and not all facilities were prepared to participate in such a platform. Since discussions for transformation of research infrastructure have been carried out at university level, it is up to the 4EU+ Alliance to foster future development and cooperation across the Alliance.

Grant Support Service (GSS) lead by Heidelberg University

The 4EU+ Alliance launched a website to bring together the pre-award infrastructure between the universities and research communities. The network of WP3 research infrastructure is involved in the process, with the WP3 lead heading the development work. Especially the opportunity to bring together researchers from different facilities with joint research ideas can be seen as a prerequisite for the workshop series mentioned earlier.

Scientific Technical Experts

During the assessment of the research infrastructure facilities and particularly within the discussions about challenges posed to international collaboration of Core Facilities, the issue of staff difficulties, also linked to funding practices, continuously came up. The project managers from all universities of the 4EU+ alliance identified the challenge of recognition and sustainable employment for experts working at the facilities at the interface of science and administration as one of the most important in the development of Core Facilities and RI facilities in general. These issues were already raised during the Conference on Educational and Research Infrastructure Collaboration in European University Alliances, which was held as part of TRAIN4EU WP6 on 8 June 2022. As already mentioned in Deliverable 3.2, especially managers and technical-scientific staff of identical or closely related research infrastructures, who are mostly running the facilities, face obstacles in terms of sustainable employment and recognition of their work. The project group of WP3 identified these staff members as “scientific technical experts” in the course of Task 3.3.

As long as such staff members face the double burden of administration of facilities and own scientific research and lack steady and recognised career paths, a sustainable and continuous network of RI facilities at local level is very challenging. This, in turn, is a hindrance to international collaborations. If the first-level challenge is to secure the funding of a research infrastructure facility and the continuation of employment, then multilateral collaboration inevitably shifts into the background. Therefore, security of career paths, possibly in combination with a degree and sustainable funding for such “scientific technical experts” should, in the WP3 group’s opinion, be addressed at the European level.

Transformative potential and impact of WP3 across 4EU+

Pilot actions at Heidelberg University:

Heidelberg University engaged in a series of meetings with Core facility managers and university administration, starting from May 2022. The WP3 lead from Heidelberg University was involved at all stages of the meetings.

Participants: Nikon Imaging Center (BioQuant), Electron Microscopy Core Facility (EMCF; Rectorate), Deep Sequencing Facility (BioQuant), Flow Cytometry & FACS Core Facility (FFCF; ZMBH), Metabolomics Core Technology Platform (MCTP; COS), University Administration Research Division.

Aim: Financial sustainability for research infrastructure facilities at Heidelberg University, including pricing for internal and external users, funding practice between first-, second and third-party funding, sustainable employment of infrastructure staff and sharing practices.

Sharing of TRAIN4EU practice: Introduction of various infrastructure facilities of the Alliance and best practice assessment from UNITECH facilities at the University of Milan, especially the centralised management model, at Heidelberg University.

At the level of the Heidelberg University administration, especially at the Research Division, the management assessment from the mapping exercise across the TRAIN4EU Universities and the management model at UNITECH were met with great interest, following a meeting with other divisional sectors (financial, legal, development). A joint user rules catalogue, including pricing arrangements, was discussed during the period May 2022 and September 2023. The main challenge identified is the broad variation across the facilities and the lack of a sustainable and long-term funding opportunity at Core facilities and other research infrastructure facilities. A joint model meets difficulties with respect to differences in management schemes and funding.

At this stage, it is not feasible to build any international network across research infrastructure facilities of the Alliance, if the local management model is still being developed, albeit being inspired by practices at other universities (e.g. University of Milan). Collaboration can nonetheless continue between facilities at this stage, which is one of the actions included in the future strategic collaboration of the 4EU+ Alliance.

Pilot actions at Charles University:

At Charles University, meetings of the European centre and the Department of Science and Research of the Rectorate of Charles University took place throughout the period covered in the report.

The results from TRAIN4EU were highlighted in the following events, which also offered networking opportunities for research infrastructure facilities at national level:

- National information day on research infrastructures, online, 28 January 2022
- Czech Days for European Research, Prague, 14 February 2023
- National conference on research infrastructures, Prague, 2 November 2023

The participation of Charles University in WP3 gave the opportunity to compare the RI management models at Charles University with those of the consortium partners, especially the best practice from UNITECH at the University of Milan. The above events also helped identify thematic overlaps that could be exploited for further integration in the future.

Pilot actions at University of Milan:

Since the University of Milan hosts the best practice facilities at UNITECH, the assessment by the TRAIN4EU group in March 2023 revealed significant potential for future collaboration, which was discussed internally before and after the meeting, including by involving colleagues from the 4EU+ universities bilaterally. Furthermore, various meetings of the UNITECH scientific committees as well as a meeting with representatives of the Lombardy Region where the university's UNITECH activities are located, took place during the reporting period.

The University of Milan is developing a new Campus (MIND) in which the creation of a new scientific macro-platform is planned, with an organisational model yet to be defined. The

work done in WP3 provides valuable insights into the realities of Core Facilities at a European level and how best to develop this new reality in Milan.

The TRAIN4EU work on Core Facilities was an objective set by the Research Directorate at the University of Milan, which evaluated and published the results in December 2023.²

Pilot actions at University of Warsaw:

Relevant meetings at the University: Apart from introducing TRAIN4EU findings at the administrative level of research infrastructure facilities, relevant meetings involved the preparation for hosting a significant event, the LERU-CE7 network meeting, where the development of research infrastructure was a key topic of discussion. During this meeting, findings from TRAIN4EU on management of research infrastructure was presented in a working group session. This meeting was part of the ongoing commitment to enhancing research capabilities through international collaboration.

Discussions on Management Models: A new code of conduct draft has been prepared, introducing a core facility model at a central level and standardizing all management rules of research infrastructure at the University of Warsaw. This approach aligns with best practices observed at UNITECH and other universities.

Impact on Research Infrastructure Development: Participation in TRAIN4EU has been instrumental in evolving the research infrastructure model of management at the University of Warsaw. It has facilitated a more structured approach to management and increased the engagement of our researchers with both academic and business sectors, thus enhancing the overall impact and efficiency of our research activities (NGS example).

Pilot actions at University of Copenhagen:

After the UNITECH assessment, the main learning points were presented to senior research and innovation administrative management. There was interest which led to revisiting how things are organized at the university today and the drawbacks of this set-up. However, for the time being it was decided not to undertake any changes because the RI structure at the University of Copenhagen (UCPH) is very complex. The UCPH de facto strategy has been to let faculties proceed on an individual basis.

There is a possible opportunity to partly proceed jointly at the university level, however. UCPH is just now after 3½ years finalizing the largescale internal research assessment process in which 40 panels of 160 foreign scientists have evaluated all research at the university. The entire material collected has been compiled into a report whose conclusions include challenges, recommendations and suggestions. Many of the suggestions are for the local / department level others are crosscutting at faculty / university level. Research infrastructure was assessed among other themes. Based on this survey, the administration together with the vice-deans for research is in the process of identifying and prioritizing cross-cutting issues that the university can choose to focus on. Research infrastructure facilities, including funding, organising and the full lifecycle are on the agenda. A number of panels have commented on the very large “variation” (pros and cons) in the way infrastructure facilities

² <https://www.unimi.it/en/research/places-organizations-and-infrastructures/unitech-facilities>

are organised/managed/given access to. Here the work of the TRAIN4EU WP3 and especially the best practice assessment provides a basis for further analysis.

Furthermore, the Danish Agency for Higher Education and Science has invited Danish research institutions to submit proposals for national research infrastructures by fall 2024. At the University of Copenhagen a considerable number of proposals for new infrastructures or substantial upgrades of existing ones is expected. In some cases, UCPH scientists will function as PIs. In other cases, UCPH will be supporting proposals for infrastructures (co)hosted by other universities. Some UCPH faculties have internal committees that carry out a pre-assessment of proposals before submission to the agency for the 2025-national Danish Roadmap. Here, first-stage scientists, who for the first time are involved in the formulation of a proposal, in some cases need inspirational material on how to organise/govern shared equipment. At this stage the results of the TRAIN4EU WP3 will be crucial for the research support units that help the scientists with drafting proposals. Here collaboration takes place with other Danish universities as the submitted proposals have to be on national level and involve several universities.³

Pilot actions at Sorbonne University:

Apart from continuous updates on the tasks in TRAIN4EU during the project lifespan, a presentation of TRAIN4EU as a whole to the research commission of Sorbonne University is envisioned for 2024. Assessment results and best practice experiences will be presented, as well as overall transformative potential of TRAIN4EU will be discussed. This presentation is an opportunity to showcase the achievements, assessment results, and best practices identified in the TRAIN4EU project. The discussion will likely involve highlighting the transformative potential of the project and its impact on research practices and outcomes. The special platform advisor of Sorbonne University is on a mission to streamline certain practices of local research platforms, however this process is ongoing and no benchmarking has been performed so far. The impact of TRAIN4EU practices is facing obstacles for the time being due to the ongoing internal actions, which are not finalised. Therefore, only a limited number of external elements are being introduced at this stage in terms of infrastructure development at Sorbonne University.

3.2. Transformative impact and future collaboration

Based on our assessment of the research infrastructure and Core Facilities at our alliance universities, we have identified potential for innovations and learning-driven transformations suitable for upscaling across the alliance with the potential for exploitation by other European Universities.

³ Link to the call – national Danish 2025-roadmap <https://ufm.dk/en/research-andinnovation/funding-programmes-for-research-and-innovation/calls/2024/call-for-proposalsroadmap-for-research-infrastructure-2025/>

Securing funding

As already established during the first monitoring of RI facilities in TRAIN4EU, in many cases the acquisition of expensive equipment is paired with problems of weak project management, finding and maintaining technical services and support staff with sufficient experience and qualifications for budgetary reasons. The funding issues often result in cost overrun or cost increase, which according to funders and university policy cannot be solved, causing equipment to become economically unviable. Costs and usage issues put pressure on and leads to competition between scientific labs and facilities, which coupled with inadequate cost division makes the scientific work less efficient. Lack of long-term financing of facilities, which is often limited to a certain period of time, results in an uncertain future and suboptimal maintenance of research infrastructure. This, in turn, poses serious obstacles to international collaboration, since funding issues are prioritised over internationalisation.

Strengthening Management

Transformative actions in research infrastructure collaboration can encompass various strategies and initiatives aimed at enhancing the effectiveness, efficiency, and impact of collaborative efforts in research infrastructure development and utilisation. Promoting the sharing of research infrastructure resources, including facilities, equipment, and expertise, among institutions and organisations can maximise utilisation and minimise duplication of efforts thus reducing costs. Interdisciplinary collaboration and integration of research infrastructure across any kind of field and discipline is the future vision of the established TRAIN4EU network, as underlined via best practice at the University of Milan. Although not all universities are prepared to implement centralised management structures, the insights from the entire group, also gained through the mapping analysis, brought various points to the attention of the working group and their respective universities.

More specifically, investing in capacity building initiatives and training programs for researchers and staff involved in research infrastructure, referred to as “scientific technical experts”, would greatly improve the quality and impact of collaborative research efforts. It has become obvious, based on the collaboration within TRAIN4EU, that engaging in international collaboration and partnerships can broaden access to specialized research infrastructure, facilitate knowledge exchange, and help leverage complementary expertise and resources from different regions and countries. Addressing regulatory barriers and promoting supportive policy frameworks for research infrastructure collaboration can facilitate cross-border cooperation, help streamline administrative processes, and incentivize investment in infrastructure development. In conclusion, management decisions are central to shaping all the factors involved in internal transformation within a university setting and hence play a key role in shaping research infrastructure transformation.

Developing Networks

The WP3 project team in TRAIN4EU will endeavour to maintain the established network and continue the extremely collegial and fruitful cooperation. While the collaboration is likely to be negatively impacted by the lack of funding, we will continue to develop cooperation possibilities within the 4EU+ Alliance in the future.

Impact of WP3 and TRAIN4EU on the 4EU+ Strategy 2025-2035

In 2023, the 4EU+ Governance started a strategic process which will lead to the launch of the new 4EU+ Strategy 2025-2035 at the end of 2024. The 4EU+ strategic ambitions are presented along four domains: education, research, innovation and global outreach. In the Research domain, results from WP3 in TRAIN4EU are included with respect to future development of the proposed pilot actions, such as workshops, joint research, infrastructure platform, funding for researchers working at RI facilities across the alliance and other opportunities arising from the WP3 network. Especially the assessment of the UNITECH Core Facilities, as well as experience from alliance partners in terms of funding, management and staff development have shown potential for the development of research collaboration in the alliance, which will be incorporated into the overall alliance strategy. Possible joint utilization of core facilities in the future, as well as shared experience on management structures, leading to shared research collaboration, is one of the strategic goals of the Alliance, building upon the networks from TRAIN4EU.

3.3. Working paper

The working paper “*Navigating the Frontier: Research Infrastructures, Core Facilities and the Shaping of a New Paradigm at European Universities.*” was written jointly by the WP participants in 2023, based on the results from WP3. All WP participants are listed as authors upon submission. The participants reviewed the text of the working paper and prepared it for submission Between April and June 2023. The paper was submitted to the European Management Journal in August 2023 and the European Journal of Innovation Management in September 2023 and to the Journal of Education Policy in October 2023. The paper has been accepted for publication with the Cogent Education Journal (after minor modifications) in April 2024.⁴

The paper addresses various challenges of research infrastructure facilities, based on the mapping and best practice assessment in WP3. Issues of sustainable funding and the challenge of long-term perspectives for infrastructure staff, referred to in WP3 as “scientific technical experts”, are also addressed. The paper abstract reads:

Research Infrastructures (RI) and Core Facilities (CF) are strong drivers for generating research results and, thus, knowledge at European Universities. In this paper, we provide insight into different features of RI and CF, their organisational structure and governance, funding mechanisms, critical factors for success, and challenges and opportunities associated with implementing and operating these research support structures. Our results are based on a comparative analysis across six European research-intensive universities from the 4EU+ University Alliance. Due to the lack of a clear definition of RI and CF, we provide a variety of indicators and criteria attributed to such facilities. We highlight differences between CF and RI in terms of goals and objectives. Establishing Core Facilities can be seen as a response to the evolving needs and challenges of researchers and academic communities at European Universities. With a centralised management and collaborative governance model, Core Facilities provide a practical solution to address these needs. We explore the legal framework,

⁴ <https://www.tandfonline.com/journals/oaed>

organisation, access, users and charge rate models at Core Facilities. We also identify several challenges in setting up and maintaining Core Facilities. Special attention is directed towards staff challenges, including introducing the staff category we identify as “scientific technical experts”. Finally, we present a Core Facility Manifesto and share our conclusions.

4. Conclusion and lessons learned

WP3 activities aimed to search for and identify promising models for sharing infrastructures across research groups and explored possibilities for joint utilisation of core facilities and other research infrastructure facilities. As a result of our efforts, we have been able to create an inventory and categorization of physical research infrastructure across 4EU+ and identified best practices for management and potential barriers for utilising, sharing and scaling infrastructure investments. This allowed us to identify potential best practices for strengthened competences and on-the-job development of the research infrastructure technical support staff, and best practice for centralised research support units.

Based on the results from Task 3.2, a co-learning effort across all six universities has taken place. Our analysis has been supported through a set of online meetings and one physical meeting at the University of Milan as best practice for centralized management units for Core Facilities. During these meetings, we have shared ideas for innovative approaches for management and support for technical infrastructure as well as support services. We have identified a new category for Core Facilities support staff which we call “scientific technical experts” and which we suggest requires attention at all European Universities and calls for possible EU action. We will continue cooperating on the development of shared resources in Core Facilities and research infrastructure facilities.

We have further engaged in consultations with selected stakeholders. Examples of potential stakeholder inclusion concern core facility management systems, such as operational software for allocation of equipment, research management solutions (e.g. support by experienced staff), collaboration platforms, and research coordination offices (fundamental service). We have found potential barriers to staff development and joint utilisation of Core Facilities, at management and funding level. We will continue to consult stakeholders to overcome obstacles for shared infrastructure development and sustainable Core Facility management.

Through exploring weaknesses in the field of common architecture of research infrastructure, as well as uncertainty with regard to maintenance and operational cost, common best practice solutions can be developed in order to address threats posed by inadequate cost division. The latter not only impacts the efficiency of the scientific work but also leads to suboptimal maintenance of research infrastructure, affecting availability to scientists and external users. However, tangible changes to infrastructure networks can only be achieved by university management and with sufficient funding.

We have learned that there is immense potential for collaboration in the research infrastructure network across European Universities. Despite many differences, there are also a number of similarities and particularly capacity for learning, especially with respect to Core Facilities and their utilisation and management. The development of staff and especially of career paths for “scientific technical experts” would have tremendous impact on the

sustainability and development of Core Facilities and would benefit from being addressed at the European level. Effective training programs and possibly a European career path and degree could help scientific technical experts maximize the use of equipment and resources, ultimately enhancing the productivity and impact of research efforts. First-stage staff development could involve offering workshops, seminars, online resources, and one-on-one assistance to enhance research infrastructure staff skills and capabilities. This would enhance continuity and sustainable know-how, which in turn could contribute to long-term maintenance of research infrastructure facilities, moving towards effective alliance collaboration.

In conclusion, the TRAIN4EU WP3 work has created a strong basis for collaboration, which will continue to evolve in the future. Through future strategic cooperation we hope to unleash the potential offered by the pooling of resources, including funding, equipment, facilities, and personnel, to support large-scale research projects that require significant investment. By sharing infrastructure, we hope to maximize the efficiency and impact of our joint research efforts in the future.

